

ARTS

RESEARCH ON ETHNIC MUSIC EDUCATION IN THE CONCEPT OF MULTICULTURALISM FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF MUSIC ANTHROPOLOGY

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Abstract

Music anthropology is a study that has attracted attention and research in China in recent years. This study's concept of multicultural music has broadened the analysis of music education in China. Therefore, the bond between music anthropology and music education has gradually deepened. This article took knowledge from music anthropology and is established with the theory of diverse music culture. The connection between music anthropology and music education, the difficulty of developing diverse music culture in China, and the significance of music education based on national culture are discussed.

We look forward to ideas for developing China's national music education to promote the prosperity and development of national music culture.

Keywords: Music Anthropology; Multiculturalism; Ethnic music education

Introduction

Today, in an era where globalization is increasing, politics, economy, technology, and culture influence each other globally. In such an environment, the concept of Multiculturalism has been present in academic thought in various fields from the perspective of cultural anthropology in recent years, providing a theoretical basis for multicultural research from the perspective of globalization. Music anthropology is an interdisciplinary study based on musicology and cultural anthropology, which is the ground knowledge in terms of research perspective and content. Regarding guiding philosophy and thinking logic, it is similar to cultural anthropology. Music anthropology advocates the study of music in the cultural category and the analysis of culture in music, that is, the study of music forms and characteristics with national culture as the core and the observation of national beliefs, humanistic feelings, and lifestyles in music. In the global cultural integration and surge process, the boundary between the "commonality" and "personality" of national culture is gradually blurring. The "cultural relativism" and "multiculturalism" emphasized in cultural anthropology have awakened national cultural identity. Cultural education and inheritance have become the focus of current cultural research. Based on the deepening connections between music anthropology and music education, music education gradually breaks away from the "European music education system" as the center of the rule. Known music anthropologist Bruno Nettl proposed "European music centralism" to expand the music education system based on the national culture⁴. From the perspective of music anthropology, multicultural music education based on cultural understanding has expanded the depth and breadth of Chinese music education. Jianhua Guan expounded on the global diversification pattern from the novel perspective of the space age and proposed that "music is a diversified human cultural practice activity and music anthropology based on the world's multicultural music is the basis of the study⁵." Multiculturalism not only recognizes culture's diver-

sity but also emphasizes culture's equality. Music education in the context of the concept of diverse music cultures in the world should also uphold respect for other ethnic music cultures while maintaining the identity of their own ethnic music culture objectively and deeply understand the world in the "differences" and "identity" of different music cultures, to break misunderstandings, to form a harmonious and stable global cultural ecological environment.

I. Research on Music Education based on Music Anthropology

Connection between Music Anthropology and Education of Music

Anthropology is a study that studies people and their culture. It is people-centered research. The basis of music anthropology is musicology. Cultural research evolved from anthropology. After all, music anthropology is inseparable from the focus on "people" and "culture." Many scholars at home and abroad compare musicology with ethnomusicology. Some scholars even believe that musicology is equivalent to ethnomusicology. Indeed, there is a great degree of commonality in research methods between the two, but it would be wrong to say they are the same. Ethnomusicology is a branch of musicology, a study to study music. Music anthropology is based on anthropological theory as the primary guide, based on the study of music as a method, and the study with the goal of understanding humans. This is the same as the "people-oriented" concept in music education. Music anthropology starts from the study of national music culture. By exploring the characteristics of national music, it uncovers the aesthetic trends, value orientations, and cultural connotations of people based on ethnic groups. The purpose of music education should also be to understand the characteristics and culture of relevant ethnic groups behind the music in the process of learning music. Through music, we can learn about the cultures of different races and regions in the world at different times. Music education from the perspective of music anthropology can open up students' horizons, help them understand the world,

break prejudices, and help them grow into complete people.

Significance of Music Education Based on Music Anthropology

Music anthropology can be defined as “the study of music in the context of culture.” Different ethnic groups uphold different ethnic beliefs and humanistic ideas. The music culture of a nation must be closely related to the local original ecological natural environment, national culture, and life phenomena. In the study of music and the culture of their people, people have innate talents. The original national musical and cultural abilities need not be built from basic knowledge. The resonance between the soul and the land exists naturally. People can be exposed to it through the process of habituation. Such action in the original ecological environment has imperceptibly affected all aspects of life, forming a cultural circle exclusive to the nation.

National culture symbolizes the unique talent and spiritual civilization of the nation. National talent is the unique ability of different ethnic groups. China is a multi-ethnic country with a vast territory. Taking different regions of China as an example, the Mongolian people are nomadic people born on the grassland. Therefore, Mongolian folk songs have a grand and majestic voice and long tunes; in comparison, the singing of folk songs in the highlands and mountainous areas of southwest, northwest, and northern China is more unrestrained. Overall, China's national music is not much affected by religious factors. Music and the land are united and celebrate people, life, and nature, reflecting the magical charm of China's land and the weather, which is also the extraordinary value of Chinese national music. Only the nation itself can maximize the cultural potential of its country. This kind of culture, which was born in different landforms and climates, is unique. Suppose the national culture loses its dominance in the nation. In that case, the cultural self-confidence of the country and the existence value of the nation will be weakened, and irreconcilable contradictions will arise within the nation.

It is precisely due to the unique talents of the nation itself that Europe has developed western music and painting to the prosperity of the world. Talent is the basis for the development of national culture, and the inheritance of generations of hard work is the crucial element for the prosperity of national culture. Suppose the nation's unique talents and native music culture are protected, inherited, and consolidated through music education. In that case, national music culture can be made the central theme of a nation, rather than focusing on the music knowledge system of other ethnic groups but weakening the development of its own national culture. From the global level, it can enhance cultural soft power, expand the influence of national values, and strengthen the right to speak internationally.

Music education and national culture must form a close connection. Learning national music culture is also a process of understanding oneself and facing up to others. The German classical aesthetics, Schiller proposed that education should cultivate a “complete personality,” which means that a person must have the

ability to think dialectically and become a person with both self-confidence and introspection or become a person with balanced development. From the perspective of the development of national music education, the same should be true.

China's current music education also attaches great importance to national music and culture education. The music curriculum standards of primary and secondary schools contain much national music and culture learning content. All conservatories have set up courses related to national music and culture, and the domestic national orchestra culture is also developing. Nevertheless, the European music knowledge system remains substantial. Suppose we can improve and establish our music knowledge system and develop it equally and in a balanced manner with the Western music knowledge system. We can thus transform national music culture into the theme of music education in Chinese music education, which has achieved the goal of prosperity and development of national culture.

Since modern China has been significantly affected by wars, most of China's national music is inseparably related to politics. National music reflects the life of a nation, and the form of national music is also associated with the state of people's lives. When China encounters aggression from other countries, the people's lives are also in dire straits. After the birth of the Communist Party, people's lives gradually stabilized, so different forms of music were produced in China at different stages. This music is full of the emotions of generations, expressing the grief of suffering, the longing for a happy life, the love and gratitude for the party, the time of labor, the joy of a good harvest, and the sweetness of encountering love.

The music that praises the Communist Party and reflects the people's lives is called the red music culture. Red music is the central theme of the current development of the motherland. At the same time, it is also a cultural symbol associated with sacrifice and grief. Countless revolutionaries have sacrificed China's development in exchange for it. The Chinese revolution is also a people's revolution. Education in red music is intended to help Chinese remember their original aspirations and to not forget their roots and past, and be grateful to their ancestors. This is the cultural role of music and the meaning of learning music in culture. Therefore, cultural inheritance is a potential cooperation between music anthropology and music education.

II. Difficulties of Development of Diverse Music Education in China

In the increasing globalization process, there has been frequent information exchange and cultural influence between ethnic groups. The integration and conflict of different ethnic groups affect the direction of history. The outbreak of war also means that different ethnic groups compete for the right to speak and the authority of their respective cultures. The winner usually occupies the profit side of cultural preservation and inheritance. Take the United Kingdom as an example. From the 1860s to the 1830s, the United Kingdom be-

came the first country in the world to complete the industrial revolution. The country's national strength grew rapidly, and it also had the strength and ambition to conquer other ethnic groups. The British colonies expanded quickly in the 19th century, extending from Europe to Asia; in addition to militarization and colonization of various countries, the British were also strong enough to bring the British education system to the colonized countries, including the British knowledge system of religion, language, history, and art. Hong Kong, China, was under British colonial rule from 1842 to 1997. Hong Kong has long implemented British-style education hence, even after Hong Kong returned to Chinese governing, many schools still use the British education system. Due to the implementation of one country, two systems, Hong Kong's Chinese history and culture education are relatively lacking compared to the mainland, which also affects the unity of national ideology, and potential contradictions and conflicts are still unavoidable. The development of national cultural inheritance in China is uneven, and many practical factors are interfering with China's cultural heritage.

Since the introduction of the European music knowledge system to China in the 20th century and the establishment of music curriculum standards by the Ministry of Education of China, China has used European music theory as the main framework for music education for many years. Western music has had a deep influence on the artistic aesthetics of Chinese people. In the first half of the 20th century, China was committed to overthrowing feudal rule and removing the old system. At that time, Western industry and military were both prosperous and developed. Therefore, China advocated the introduction of Western studies, which also brought Western music culture. People are so hungry for new things and the external culture that this even leads to blind worship. At that time, China did not have a sound music knowledge system, and the society was in turmoil for a long time. The domestic music education system needed a better space and environment for development. China is vast, and it is more difficult to unify the music education system. In contrast, the European music knowledge system has been relatively sound, so the music culture under the European knowledge system has achieved considerable development in China. Today, people still equate music genres such as art songs and symphonies from Europe with "high art" and believe Western music is the authority and benchmark of music. Many outstanding works of Western music from the Baroque period to the Romantic period have been passed down by later generations and eventually affected the world. China's music education has a more mature learning system for western music history, and academic research has been refined to different periods, genres, and musicians. Although the study of Chinese music history has been vigorously promoted in recent years, it is still difficult to shake the central position of western music culture in the Chinese music education system.

It can be seen from Bruno Nettle's postmodern music education that he strongly advocates the concept of diverse musical culture education and believes that equal musical and cultural exchanges should be carried

out between ethnic groups. He explained from the perspective of the Western world what is the concept of diverse music culture, that is, not putting the status of one's own music culture above other ethnic groups. Learning the music of one ethnic group is equivalent to understanding the culture of one ethnic group. Understanding other ethnic groups means knowing the world, and the process of knowing the world is also knowing oneself. From the Western perspective of diverse music culture, what is lacking is the study and exploration of the world and an outward outlook. It is a view of pride and prejudice, not a "denigrate." China's concept of diverse music culture should be considered from the perspective of Western opposition. China lacks the ability to understand the world and the motivation to understand oneself. It is a view to enhancing cultural identity and self-esteem, not a "panegyricize."

The main difficulties in China's diverse music education are not external but internal factors. This is similar to many other developing countries. From the perspective of cultural inheritance, many countries are no longer colonized by Western countries in the sense of the land but still accept the "cultural colonization" under the influence of Western universal values. However, the author does not think that we should abandon Western music culture as a result. Multiculturalism is not to abandon other cultures and maintain our national culture but to balance the weight of our national culture and other national cultures with an attitude of all development. The best way to establish a national music knowledge system is to enhance the nation's musical culture and inner self-esteem. Not being strong enough is the primary obstacle to the development and inheritance of national culture.

III. Strategies for Developing China's Diverse music Education

Establishing China's independent music education knowledge system

As mentioned earlier, the main problem for advancement of China's diverse music education comes from the lack of internal cultural awareness, which conflicts with the equality of diverse music education. Paying too much attention to the Western music education knowledge system has led to misunderstandings and deviations in the music cognition of our people. To develop diversified music education, we must first solve our internal problems. How can a nation that does not respect itself respect other nations?

From the perspective of the world, the establishment of China's independent music education system is necessary to remove "European music centralism" and build the basic theoretical knowledge structure of its music. From the country's perspective, it is necessary to remove the "Han music centralism" and integrate and summarize multi-ethnic music culture to form a music knowledge system that belongs to China.

Deepen Related Music Education Courses

The central idea of diversified music education is to establish an education system free of racial, regional,

and cultural discrimination. In diversified music education, it is necessary to reflect the equality of the music culture of all ethnic groups and not emphasize the authority of any music culture system. At the same time, to show the objective, rational learning and integration of the world's ethnic music culture.

From China's current music education perspective, music education courses offer courses related to world-ethnic music. However, concept-based indoctrination education does not combine the common role of multi-ethnic music culture, and it has not completely transformed the development of human culture in the world. In conclusion, diversified music education is not a single and independent study of different ethnic music cultures but integration and comparison of the music cultures of different ethnic groups, exploring the truth of human development from differences and commonalities, cultivating students' speculative ability from music education and exploring the essence of insight from music events.

If China's diverse music education is to develop, it is first necessary to strengthen the in-depth relevance of the world's ethnic music education curriculum. The equality advocated by diverse music education is also conducive to enhancing the consciousness of China's local music culture. Starting from the official education system is the most direct and effective way of development.

Conclusions

Culture is the symbolic feature that distinguishes a nation from other nations, and it embodies the eternal truth that a nation pursues. The study of music anthropology attaches great importance to the connection between music and human culture. The study of music education is human-centered. These two studies can be cross-applied harmoniously, opening up a deeper perspective on music education. The theory of diverse music culture in music anthropology is the central thesis of music anthropology. It advocates an equal and objective perspective to study the culture of one's nation and other nations. This is also the concept pursued by

music education, that is, through music education, to shape a more confident and calm personal quality while enhancing the cultural value and influence of a nation. Music education in culture is the current focus of attention. Implementing music education centered on national culture is significant to establishing China's music education system. Music education based on the concept of music anthropology is a forward-looking research object and is expected to become an important thrust and theoretical support for the prosperity and development of national music culture.

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